

PROBLEMS OF PLANNING ENGLISH LESSONS

Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova¹

¹Associate Professor of Tashkent State Transport University

ORCID identifier: 0000-0002-6535-0197

Email: SHAHLO-70@mail.ru

Khusanova Indira²

²Teacher of Tashkent State Transport University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7337314>

Abstract: This article describes the recommendations on the correct planning of lessons and methods of solving planning problems in the organization of foreign language lessons. It is also explained how important foreign languages are in the education system.

Key words: foreign languages, skills, law on education, analysis of planned lesson, English language, methodology.

The methodology of teaching foreign languages is one of the most important factors, as the main task of general secondary education schools. This issue is at the center of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic. There are all conditions for educating students of general education schools and for them to master foreign languages. Specialists are doing great work in the field of teaching foreign languages. Educational programs have been created for all classes. Pedagogical technologies are being created in order to demonstrate knowledge, skills, and abilities in students. Therefore, the foreign language lesson differs from other educational subjects in two aspects, that is, the purpose and content of the lesson. If the foreign language teacher is able to plan the lesson and the types of lessons, as well as plan the foreign language lesson and organize the lesson in accordance with the requirements of the time and the purpose of the lesson, the effectiveness of the lesson and the final result are guaranteed. When planning a foreign language lesson at the initial stage of foreign language teaching, planning the organization of a foreign language lesson, planning the lesson taking into account the knowledge levels of the students in the class, being well aware of the conditions of teaching, psychological laws, and the stages of formation of speech skills. to know the basic requirements for a modern foreign language lesson.

If we list the modern requirements for the lesson:

- 1) the main goals of the lesson are to create skills and competences, not to explain the rules (information) about a foreign language,
- 2) the speech process is imitated from the communicative direction to the speech practice exercises,

- 3) the methodical organization of the foreign language material in the lesson takes place in the form of a whole (the speech sample is considered a unit based on all the exercises),
- 4) each type of speech activity is studied with the help of a suitable exercise system,
- 5) the lesson will have a single leading goal and auxiliary goals,
- 6) lesson effectiveness is measured by student activity,
- 7) control in the lesson is meaningful,
- 8) whenever possible, the lesson is conducted in a foreign language,
- 9) with the help of the content of the educational material, carefully developed methodical methods and demonstration, students are taught to be interested and seek knowledge.

The main purpose of lesson planning is the goal, tasks, volume of language material, the sequence of inclusion in the lesson process and, accordingly, formation of speaking skills. It is necessary to be able to determine in advance the difficulties that may arise in planning and to prepare the ways of its elimination and the corresponding exercises. The difficulty of a foreign language is taken into account by the author of the textbook when creating exercises. When the teacher prepares for the educational material of this lesson, he analyzes the comparison of native language and foreign language phenomena. He increases his attention to those small language units, and if necessary, introduces additional exercises. Ensuring a sequence of exercises.

Choosing equipment for the lesson. During the preparation for the lesson, special attention is paid to the choice of educational tools. Sufficient and necessary equipment is prepared depending on the purpose of the lesson, new material, exercises and the level of students. Technical and simple, educational methodical complex and hand-made audiovisual tools and methods of using them are thought out. The behavior and actions of the teacher and students are carefully thought out in preparation for the lesson. The teacher should have professional pedagogical skills (planning, research, organization and training), methodical skills (knowledge of learning language, mastery theory, age and personality characteristics of students). Having mastered planning skills, the teacher will be able to choose language materials, teach, interact with students, and organize the lesson. In the modern foreign language teaching methodology, it is recommended to solve the issues of lesson planning and preparation for the lesson based on the "Didactic Analysis" model. When preparing for the lesson, the teacher answers several questions and makes a number of decisions.

"Didactic analysis" model allows to make methodically based decisions. The teacher will be able to carefully consider each decision in turn. The "Didactic Analysis" model shows how the teacher makes decisions and their sequence when preparing for the lesson. But the teacher should also know how the learning process goes, what stages the lesson is divided into, and how these stages are implemented in sequence. During the planning phase, the teacher asks: "What should the students learn?", "What should the students do?" divided into groups or"; "What is the student's activity carried out with the help of?", what teaching tools, aids and materials are provided to the students for the lesson, answering the question "What should the teacher do" and should find a solution to these questions. In short, the teacher's approach to each methodical stage of the lesson should be maximally thought out and directed to achieve the goal. The exercises that should be used in the practice of each student will develop his Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities. As much as the lesson is designed in different ways, different from each other and interesting to the student, it becomes a product of the teacher's creative approach.

References:

1. INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH; Kharatova Sh.Kh; "Экономика и социум" 3 (82) 2021 www.iupr.ru
2. "THE IMPORTANCE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS" KHARATOVA SHAKHLO KHAKIMOVA; "SCIENCE AND EDUCATION" IN VOLUME #2 ISSUE #5, MAY 2021;
3. "PROBLEMS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND ITS SOLUTION" Kharatova Shakhlo Khakimovna; «Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире» ISCIENCE.IN.UA Выпуск 4(72) ч. Стр 60; ISSN 2524-0986.
4. Харатова Ш.Х. ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ СПОСОБЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА; Academy 2 (53) «Олимп» 2020;
5. Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova; TENDENCIES OF DEVELOPMENT OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN GLOBAL TRANSFORMATION; Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences 10. 2021;
6. Kharatova Shakhlo "USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS" Science and Education ISSUE 3, March 2022;
7. Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova "Goals And Tasks Of English Language Teaching" International Bulletin Of Engineering And Technology Volume 2, Issue 9, September;
8. Shakhlo Khakimovna Kharatova "THE ROLE OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE PROJECTS AND TECHNOLOGIES" IBAST | Volume 2, Issue 10, October 2022.

9. Kharatova Shakhlo Khakimovna CHARACTERISTICS OF DIFFERENT AGE GROUPS LEARNING ENGLISH Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning (EJEDL), In Volume 3, Issue 10 2022.

